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Public Spaces and Street Vendors in Mumbai A Theoretical Understanding of Urban Reciprocity

Ar. Jwalant Dave

Assistant Professor, Rizvi College of Architecture, Mumbai
emailjwalantdave@gmail.com

Ar. Urvashi Purohit

Assistant Professor, Aditya College of Architecture, Mumbai
urvashipurohit@gmail.com

Ar. Mayuresh Gorey

Associate Professor, D.Y. Patil College of Architecture, Mumbai
mayureshgorey86@gmail.com

Abstract:

Street vending is not only one of the most prominent, observable and prevalent forms of the informality in urban areas; it is also one of the most resilient forms of the informal urban economy. It contributes towards the generation of economic activity at the neighborhood scale and also adds value to urban living by providing a necessary convenience of more direct access to numerous commodities and services for a far wider demographic spectrum than addressed by most formal means of distribution. This research focuses on the city of Mumbai, the financial capital of India, and attempts to identify the specific relationships that street vending activities develop with the public spaces within which they are conducted and the impacts it has on these spaces. It also investigates the influence that the physical form and spatial characteristics of the public space have on the type of vending activity and the manner in which it is conducted. The research examines the existing policies and legislation that govern street vending in India, as well as the specific scenarios that exist as the ground reality for street vending activities. It also relies on available scholarly literature and established theoretical concepts to develop a methodology to study these specific scenarios and identify the nature of the intrinsic interdependence between urban public spaces and street vending activities. A matrix of evaluation is derived from this methodology and applied to various areas of the city where street vending is prevalent to obtain and analyze tangible and measurable data. The findings reveal identifiable patterns of street vending associated with specific typologies of public spaces and these are organized into distinct categories. The research concludes with specific recommendations for developing a regulatory tool kit that addresses the needs and concerns of street vending activities in the context of the particular public spaces that host them while also ensuring that other activities of a public nature that are conducted in the same public spaces are not impacted adversely.

Keywords: *street vending; urban informal economy; public spaces; social inclusion; regulatory controls*

1. Introduction:

Informal economic activities are having a market value but do not directly contribute to the tax revenue of a city/state/nation, since they are not recorded. The International Labor Organization estimated (in early 2021) that about 60% of the global work force and about 80% of global enterprises were, at least partially, part of the informal sector of the global economy. The Indian economy has been classified as an *Emerging Market and Developing Economy* by the IMF in their *World Economic Outlook Database* published in October 2022, and ranked as the fifth largest economy on the global scale in the same database. At the same time, India ranks significantly lower on GDP per capita share (due to its large population and the increasing disparity in wealth distribution across the population).

1.1 Informal economies of Urban Street Vendors:

Informal economic activities in Indian cities manifest in myriad forms, with one of the most visible and vital forms that is evident across cities being that of the *Street Vending*. Street vendors form an integral component of the urban economy making it dynamic and flexible by hawking their goods and services to potential customers, in public spaces that are well frequented by people and see extremely high footfall, thus literally bringing the market to their customers rather than having the customers come to the market. Street vending proliferates directly at the locality level and thus helps create a robust mechanism of urban growth and resilience, while adding vibrancy and social energy to public spaces that are not only inherently active due to high footfall, have a high degree of accessibility (physical, financial, temporal and universal), have greater safety, but are also more inclusive and diverse in terms of usage and more recognizable within the larger context of the city itself.

1.2 Problem Statement:

Street vending contributes substantially to the social and economic vitality of urban public space and is instrumental in defining the spatial character of the public realm by shaping the lived reality of public spaces. While this demonstrates the inherent plurality and social inclusivity of public spaces it also highlights the central role that regulatory frameworks need to play in ensuring equitable access to these spaces and upholding the public right to inhabit and occupy them, as theorized by Edward W. Soja in his book “Seeking Spatial Justice”.

1.3 Area of Concern:

Street vending is observed to be intrinsically entwined with the spatial character of public spaces and often endows them with their unique identities, thus necessitating it to be systematically integrated into these spaces. This can be achieved through a robust and dynamic legislative framework that governs not only the social and functional/economic dimensions of the activity but extends beyond to regulate the morphological/physical dimension of the activity. This would effectively integrate the vending activity with the physical realm within which it is conducted, thus imparting flexibility and plurality of use.

1.4 Aim of Research:

The research aims to establish the relationship between the informal socioeconomic activity of street vending and the legislative and regulatory framework necessitated by it to favourably optimize the use of urban public spaces as socially plural and multifunctional realms of the city.

1.5 Research Question(s):

Main research question:

- What is the nature of reciprocity in the relationship between street vending activities and public spaces in metropolitan cities such as Mumbai?

Research sub-questions:

- What are the identifiable characteristics of public spaces that act as enabling factors for conducting the activity of street vending within them?
- What are the scales of public space at which street vending activities thrive?
- How does the scale of the public space influence the types/variety/diversity and the
- Magnitude/concentration/volume of street vending activity conducted within it?

1.6 Research Objectives:

- To identify the reciprocity in the relationship between urban public spaces and street vending.
- To identify the scales of urban public space that supports this reciprocal influence.
- To determine the relationship of proportionality between the location and scale of the public space and the diversity and magnitude of street vending that occurs within it

1.7 Hypothesis:

Street vendors in cities such as Mumbai, provide an essential means of distributing a host of goods and services directly to end consumers, becoming a necessary convenience of access and significantly adding value to urban living.

Therefore, street vending needs to be acknowledged as an urban value added activity that has a legitimate right to the public spaces that it is conducted within for optimal access to the end consumers.

1.8 Significance of Study:

Street vending is not only one of the most visible forms of the informal economy in urban areas, but due to this visibility is also one of the most vulnerable forms of informal economic activity. The social perception of street vending is also significantly polarized with frequent and volatile fluctuations between protection and persecution, often existing in a fluid state of negotiated tolerance.

Moreover, while the past decade, particularly in the wake of the COVID19 pandemic and consequent lockdowns, has seen significant and positive transformation in the government's stance towards street vending by initiatives such as the provision of; legislative protection through the *Street Vendors (Protection of Livelihood and Regulation) Act, 2014*, financial inclusivity through schemes such as *Pradhan Mantri Street Vendors Atmanirbhar Nidhi Yojna* and social welfare through the *Support to Urban Street Vendors (SUSV) under the Deendayal Antyodaya Yojana National Urban Livelihoods Mission*; these measures remain largely on paper and the policy framework has not translated to benefits on ground for the street vendors. It is therefore imperative to understand the potential of utilizing these legislative initiatives to create an inclusive and progressive socioeconomic environment that positively affects the integration of this most prominent facet of the informal economy into the formal economy at the local, national and global levels.

1.9 Scope:

This research focuses on studying the various manifestations of the activity of street vending and includes the diversity of locations, modes and products that are observed in urban street vending in India. Further, the research focuses on street vending from the lenses of sociology, economics and legislation to establish the degrees of reciprocity that exist between the activity and the space that it inhabits.

1.10 Limitations:

This research is restricted to studying street vending activities within the jurisdictional boundaries of the Municipal Corporation of Greater Mumbai (MCGM) while taking references of global, national and local examples in order to ensure a focused and localized study of a diverse and global phenomenon. The research does not specifically view the political dimension independently and instead studies the political implications and influences on street vending through the sociological, economic and legislative dimensions.

2. Literature Review:

The research reviews available scholarly academic literature on street vending as an urban activity as well as existing legislation and policy framework for street vending in India, while applying the lenses of sociology, economics and legislation to understand not only the role that street vending plays in cities, but also the ways in which it shapes urban life and urban public spaces where it is conducted. The literature has been categorized according to key themes that illustrate the underlying mechanisms through which street vending activities and public spaces influence each other, and organizes the inferences so as to develop a clear understanding of the of sociological, economic and legislative importance of street vending as an urban phenomenon.

2.1 Sociological Perspective:

Understanding street vending, its types and distribution:

The existence of street vending can be traced through the history of human civilization, across different cultures and countries, adding vitality to a city's public spaces and generates economic activity at the local scale of the neighbourhood. The situation of street vending as observed in India confirms that it is more prevalent in urban settlements, with Central Government data from 2017-18 showing about 90% of the workforce being employed in the informal sector and about 14% of this being street vendors. Street vending is an informal enterprise that can operate at significantly smaller scales requiring minimal financial investment, making it especially attractive to migrants and other urban poor who cannot afford other means of enterprise and usually lack adequate education to be absorbed into the formal economy.

The Street Vendors Act of 2014 uses spatial criteria and takes into consideration the distribution and concentration of street vendors in a public space. It identifies four typologies of vending zones as; *Public Spaces* (open spaces within the city that are accessible to the public and primarily serve the purpose of passive and active recreation); *Natural Markets* (neighbourhoods that have traditionally hosted formal markets, retail and commercial activities within the city and are identified as the city's commercial hubs); *Streets* (the axes within the city that provide movement and access to various modes of transportation within particular neighbourhoods); and *Railway Stations* (the primary transportation hubs within a city).

The National Policy on Urban Street Vendors, 2009, uses the status of mobility and adaptability of the street vending activity to identifies three typologies of vending based on the type of cart/stall/kiosk that is used by the street vendor. *Stationary* vendors, who have a fixed stall at a specific location; *Peripatetic* vendors, who tend to carry out the vending by moving from place to place and time to time with a moveable cart or stall; and

Mobile vendors, who move around across a place and constantly circulate as they vend from a mobile cart or bicycle mounted stall. A number of scholarly research papers also classify street vending activities in a similar manner, describing the stalls variously as “kiosks, heavy stalls, heavy mobile stalls, pushcarts or stalls on wheels, etc.” or as “fixed, semi-fixed and mobile or itinerant vendors”

These methods of classification demonstrate that while street vending appears to be a largely uniform and homogeneous phenomenon, in practice it is a complex activity comprising an extremely broad spectrum of legal, albeit, informal trade activities, manifesting in a diversity of forms and modes. Street vending is therefore perceived to be a pervasive and resilient activity that without adequate regulation permeates into most of the available public spaces and proliferates a form of urban informality at the most local scale in the city. This perpetuates a negative perception of street vending resulting in public attitude towards street vendors fluctuating constantly between *protection* and *persecution*.

Perceived social ramifications of street vending:

The opposition to street vending primarily appears to stem from its perceived illegality and unregulated nature of operations, and often manifests from four directions; first, as being detrimental to the value of a neighbourhood; second, as being a nuisance to the well-being of local residents and businesses; third, as being the primary cause of chaos on public roads, streets and opens spaces; and fourth, as being damaging to the environment due to the lack of accountability for managing the waste it generates. This is especially evident in neighbourhoods where a large number of stakeholders having specific but often conflicting interests, focus their attention on the street vending activities attributing to them any observed disorder, congestion, pollution and a general unsightliness. Such areas are predominantly the central business districts, neighbourhood level commercial centres or retail spines, transportation terminals and recreational spaces such as sports centres, entertainment centres and tourist attractions, and have been identified as “conflict zones” by Bromley (1978, 2000). It is interesting to note that these correspond directly with the four typologies of vending zones classified by the Street Vendors Act of 2014.

The support for street vending, on the other hand, appears to stem primarily from the perspective of humanitarian values and economics, usually manifesting from four directions; first, as a right of all citizens, especially the most marginalized and poor, to be able to practice an occupation involving the trade of legal goods and services as a livelihood; second; as a form of social welfare that brings together various stakeholders in a neighbourhood creating social and economic linkages between them; third, as an economic activity that contributes directly to the widest spectrum of the local demography while encouraging entrepreneurship within the neighbourhood communities and generating innovative ideas for new enterprises; and fourth, as a politically beneficial stance to endorse the idea of the right to livelihood for all citizens, and a political opportunity to win the favour of a significant urban constituency.

Innovation, Adaptability and Resilience of Street Vending in urban areas:

As observed earlier, street vending is one of the most innovative, adaptable, and resilient forms of the informal urban economy being a vital component of the larger urban ecology as one of the most efficient mechanisms to distribute essential products and services to the widest spectrum of the urban demography including citizens who may lack access to formal channels of distribution. Street vendors’ associations, having large numbers of members often exercise some degree of negotiation with local authorities and other government bodies. These associations may also leverage a greater degree of access to formal financing for their individual members.

Additionally, local non-governmental organizations concerned with the general welfare of the city and its population, especially the most vulnerable sections, also provide much needed professional support. Street vendors also tend to be fiercely territorial of their pitches and often have conflicts among themselves over the right to conduct their trade at a particular place. Such issues are less prominent in the case of street vendors

who have established themselves over a number of years and are generally recognized as much for their location than for their wares.

In certain cases, formal retail and commercial establishments develop a mutually beneficial relationship with street vendors allowing specific vendors to operate in front of the formal establishments. This helps in attracting more footfall for both and provides customers of either with value addition from the other. Garment shops often allow tailors to set up outside their premises allowing them access to infrastructure such as power and water, in order to provide their customers with the value added service of alterations which they may themselves not offer.

2.2 Economic Perspective:

Reasons for the emergence of street vending in urban public spaces:

The factors that lead to the emergence of street vending in public spaces tend to be primarily economic in nature, and may arise from a variety of situations such as, migration to urban areas to escape poverty, loss of employment in a formal sector of the economy, lack of alternative employment in public or private sector enterprises and the attraction of starting up a business, albeit informal, with minimal financial inputs and risks.

Perceived economic ramifications of street vending:

Street vending is sometimes perceived to be an unfair competition to formal retail and commercial establishments since it operates without the overheads of rent for space, staff and access charges for infrastructure services such as power, water, sewerage and waste disposal. Moreover, since street vendors rarely provide any guarantees to back their wares, this is also seen to be an unfair advantage favouring street vending.

This leads to stigmatization and stereotyping of street vendors as sellers of substandard products and services, affecting them negatively and excluding them further from the formal economy. Financial exclusion also occurs due to the lack of regulated and government backed welfare schemes that provide vital services such as credit, insurance and microfinance.

The link between access to such financial services and economic growth through formalization and financial inclusion is an observed and established fact. Further, research has also established a clear link between the availability of microfinance through Micro Finance Institutions (private sector financing entities) and the reduction of poverty.

2.3 Legislative Perspective:

Necessity for legislation of street vending activities:

In India, the Street Vendors (Protection of Livelihoods and Regulation of Street Vending) Act, 2014, provides the legislative support required to protect the rights of street vendors to conduct street vending as their livelihood activity and is a first step towards the gradual integration of street vending into the formal economy. It also provides the framework required to develop specific regulations and controls for street vending within the administrative jurisdiction of cities and places the onus on urban local bodies (local or municipal authorities) to develop and implement such regulations. The complexities of developing regulations that address an extremely broad range of scenarios and involve multiple stakeholders with diverse and often conflicting interests, have constrained urban local bodies from developing and implementing such regulations. A deeper understanding of street vending activities and their relationship with urban public spaces, while fundamental to the development of any comprehensive regulations, is severely lacking.

This makes it a concern of urgent importance, both to address the livelihood needs of street vendors, and to address the larger planning needs of the city, such as developing integrated and inclusive design strategies that promote the inclusive and balanced growth of the city by enhancing the quality of the public spaces, leading to a more supportive and inclusive urban economy that protects the rights of all citizens, especially the street vendors who have so far been neglected and excluded from integration into the formal economy.

Challenges in regulating street vending activities:

The Street Vendors Act, 2014 mandates every urban local body to form a Town Vending Committee, but only a few cities have succeeded in this. Most, including the Municipal Corporation of Greater Mumbai, have even struggled with conducting accurate census surveys or documenting the existing situation of street vending in the city.

Figure 1: Production of urban space (Source: Author)

Complexities in drafting appropriate regulatory framework:

The process of drafting an appropriate regulatory framework for street vending in urban public spaces, that addresses the diverse interests of all stakeholders, and also ensures the minimization of the impact of any one stakeholder activity on others is a complex task, and requires a broad study of the diversity of expression in street vending, its intrinsic relationship to the public spaces and its impacts on other public activities.

		Parameters Derived from Conceptual Framework							
		Key Concepts	Attributes/ Characteristics	Tangible/ Quantitative	Intangible/ Qualitative	Street Vending	Variables	Indicators	
QUALITY OF OUTDOOR SPACE AFFECTS DEGREE OF OUTDOOR ACTIVITY	Life Between Buildings <i>Jan Gehl</i>	Necessary Activities	Minimum dependence on External Influences, such as : Time, Place and People Planned, <i>ROUTINE</i>	✓	✗	Daily shopping: Groceries such as : (Vegetables, Fruits, Dairy, Eggs, Fish, Meat, etc.)	Vicinity to point of source (home/work/etc.)	Number of vendors/ Frequency of visiting Time spent in shopping	
		Optional Activities	Moderate dependence on External Influences, such as : Time, Place and People Planned, <i>VOLUNTARY</i>	✗	✓	Occasional Shopping: Clothing items, mobile accessories, etc.	Identity of vending area from type of product sold there	Time of day of visiting?	
		Social Activities	Maximum dependence on External Influences, such as : Time, Place and People Spontaneous, <i>RESULTANT</i>	✓	✓	Incidental Shopping: Tea, snacks, etc.	Familiarity of vending area and vendors	Number of contacts Duration of Contact during visits	
Dichotomy of Perception									
CAPITALISM INTRINSICALLY DEPENDENT ON PRODUCTION OF URBAN SPACE AND HENCE GROWTH OF CITIES	The Production of Space <i>Henri Lefebvre</i>	Perceived Space	Power, Scarcity, Identity, Safety, Status, etc.	✗	✓	Sociological Perception of Street Vending: As a contributor to vitality and safety in public spaces. OR As a contributor to illegality and conflict in public spaces.	Cleanliness at vending area	Number of garbage bins available	
		Lived Space	Space as Capital, Monetary value	✓	✗	Economic Perception of Street Vending: As a contributor to the generation of economic activity at the informal level. OR As a competitor to the organization of economic activity at the formal level	Volume of sales at vending area	Number of Customers/ Footfall	
		Conceived Space	Measurement, Dimensions, Boundaries	✓	✓	Legislative Perception of Street Vending: As a means of livelihood that has legal protection OR As a public nuisance that is an illegal occupant of public space	Congestion, Crowding at vending area	Number of stalls per square unit length Size of stalls	
Informality of Operation									
THE SPATIALITY OF JUSTICE AFFECTS SOCIETY AND SOCIAL LIFE AS MUCH AS THE SOCIAL PROCESSES SHAPE THE SPATIALITY OF URBAN SPACE	Seeking Spatial Justice <i>Edward W. Soja</i>	Freedom as predominantly economic notion that does not affect geography	Legislative production of urban growth	✓	✗	Right to Livelihood without the right to public space for conducting livelihood activity of street vending	Legality of vending	Status of notification of vending area	
		Justice as a concept more effective in addressing the social cleavages of class, race(cast) and gender	Social production of urban growth	✗	✓	Projection of social discrimination of class, cast and gender onto vending zones and street markets as poorer spaces of the city	People's perception of safety within vending area	Limitations on access based on gender, class, etc	
		Collective right to urban space most effectively addressed at regional scales	Economic production of urban growth	✓	✓	Right to space embedded within the physical dimensions of public spaces instead of limiting access to only defined vending zones	Factors enabling vending activities	Availability of infrastructure for vending activities (power, water, sewerage, waste disposal, etc.)	
Ambiguity of Regulation									

IDENTIFICATION OF VARIABLES AND INDICATORS FOR STUDYING VENDING ACTIVITIES

Figure 2: Identification of variables and indicators for studying vending activities (Source: Author)

2.4 Conceptual Framework:

The principles proposed by Jan Ghel in *Life Between Buildings: Using Public Space* (originally published in Danish in 1971 by Arkitektens Forlag, first translated to English and published in 1987 by Van Nostrand Reinhold, New York) are applied to street vending in order to understand its role in encouraging Social Activities that happen within public spaces. The research categorizes street vending into *Necessary Shopping Activities* (e.g. shopping groceries and food items, usually performed daily) and *Optional Shopping Activities* (e.g. shopping clothes and accessories, usually performed weekly or monthly) and investigates their influence on increasing *Social Activities* that happen within any public space. These activities are measured using the three metrics of *Density, Diversity and Duration* of street vending since these three indicators are directly proportional to the number of opportunities of social interaction that happen while conducting the necessary or optional shopping activities.

By applying Henri Lefebvre's *Production of Space* theory to the study of urban street vendors, the research distinguishes the use of urban public space by the street vendors for vending activities into three distinct yet intertwined methods that correspond with the three categories of space defined by the theory. These are elaborated as:

The Perceived Space:

This is the way humans associate abstract values to space. It involves the association of concepts such as power, sanctity, etc.

SOCIOLOGICAL perception of space is explored through this category.

The Conceived Space:

This is the way humans quantify and define space. It employs processes such as measuring and surveying space, drawing boundaries to define it, allocating uses to it, etc.

LEGISLATIVE perception of space is explored through this category.

The Lived Space:

This is the way humans actually use and live within the space. It brings together the conceived and perceived aspects and is often the way that humans utilize space as capital, to create monetary value from the space, etc. Economic perception of space explored through this category. The research also applies the concept of "Spatial Justice" as proposed by Edward W. Soja in his book *Seeking Spatial Justice* (University of Minnesota Press, 2010; reprinted 2013). The research methodology is principally structured around understanding urban public space used for street vending through the three key aspects concerning the activity of street vending, i.e. the legislative perspective, the social perspective and the economic perspective.

The above three theories are applied in unison to derive a cohesive framework within which the interactions between street vending activities and the public spaces that host these activities are studied to understand the intrinsic spatial relationships between them. This framework is further utilized to determine a comprehensive set of parameters and define the observable and measurable indicators of these parameters, in order to systematically study specific districts which, support the various modes of street vending observed in the city.

The research is informed by the literature review as well as the existing legislative framework for street vending in India, to identify the four typologies of public spaces within a city where street vending activities are predominantly observed; *Public Open Spaces, Natural Markets, Streets, and Railway Stations*.

Figure 3: Typologies of vending zones (Source: Author)

The research also utilizes the six dimensions of urban design as defined by Matthew Carmona in the book *Public Places - Urban Spaces* (Routledge, 2003, 2012) to create a matrix of study within which the indicators derived through the conceptual framework are placed and the matrix is applied to specific examples of each of the four identified typologies of street vending zones within the city.

Figure 4: Vending pitches in wards (Source: MCGM Hawking Pitches Database)

The Municipal Corporation of Greater Mumbai’s database of identified vending pitches in Mumbai is utilized to select the specific examples of the four vending zone typologies. The H-West and K-West administrative wards are selected for the study due to; the geographical adjacency of both wards; the contrast in the geographical size and population density of both wards; the diversity of development (residential, commercial, mixed use, social amenities and recreation) within both wards; the presence of well-developed network of transport within both wards and good degree of connectivity with the rest of the city through these networks; and most importantly the presence of all four typologies in relative proximity to each other in both wards.

Figure 5: Methodology of study (Source: Author)

3. Methodology of Study:

The research also adopts a distinct methodology from each of the three theoretical backgrounds of the conceptual framework in conjunction with the legislative framework of “The Street Vendors (Protection of Livelihoods and Regulation of Street Vending) Act 2014, to address the three distinct lenses (sociological, economic and legislative) used to study the phenomenon of street vending.

In each case, the demographic and spatial implications of street vending when perceived through that particular lens are identified and utilized to define the specific purpose and type of data to be collected, as well as the process and methods to be used for collecting this data.

Sociological Perspective:

By using the theoretical background proposed by Jan Gehl in *Life between Buildings*, the research identifies *adequate access and diverse distribution of goods and services* as the demographic implication and views the role of street vending as *a necessary activity for urban life* as the spatial implication. The purpose of the data here is to provide observable information about the *locations that are conducive to supporting high volumes of street vending activities*, with the process of data collection being the *study of customers' perceptions* and the method of data collection being *surveys*.

Economic Perspective:

By using the theoretical background proposed by Henri Lefebvre in *The Production of Space*, the research identifies *economic growth through income generation opportunities* as the demographic implication and views the role of *street vending as a formalized activity for the urban economy* as the spatial implication. The purpose of the data here is to provide observable information about the *patterns of spatial distribution of street vending activities that optimize economic opportunity*, with the process of data collection being the *study of density, diversity and duration of street vending activities* and the method of data collection being *through a study of the six dimensions of urban design*.

Legislative Perspective:

By using the theoretical background proposed by Edward W. Soja in *Seeking Spatial Justice*, the research identifies *the right to livelihood* as the demographic implication and views the role of *regulations in endowing street vending activities the right to occupy public space* as the spatial implication. The purpose of the data here is to provide observable information about *land use planning that enables the attraction and flow of footfall*, with the process of data collection being the *study of linkages, blockages, convergences and divergences of street vending activities as a direct result of land use planning* and the method of data collection being *through a study of the presence of land use magnets and transportation routes of the footfall*.

3.1 Land Use:

Land Use Magnets:

In a typical urban scenario, land uses such as *Commercial, Transportation and Social Amenities*, act as *magnets* and attract large volumes of *footfall* to the interconnecting street networks.

Footfall Linkages:

These *magnets* have their own influence areas, and play a crucial role in determining the volume and direction of the flow of *footfall*. They form important *linkages* for vending

Impact on Street Vending:

The streets carrying the *footfall* around these *magnets* become ideal spaces to support Street Vending, and directly influence the Density, Diversity and Duration of Vending Activities.

Figure 6: Transportation hub, social amenities, commercial premises, public spaces with potentially high footfall (Source: Author)

Diagram showing the extents and overlaps in influence zones of different land use magnets, and public spaces most likely to host high footfall due to these land use magnets

3.2 Six Dimensions of Urban Design:

MORPHOLOGICAL	VISUAL	FUNCTIONAL	SOCIAL	TEMPORAL	PERCEPTUAL
PHYSICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF VENDING LOCATIONS	METHODS ADOPTED FOR OPTIMIZING VISIBILITY	PHYSICAL DIMENSIONS OF VENDORS' CARTS/STALLS	PERCENTAGES OF TYPES OF INTERACTION ENABLED	PATTERNS OF OPERATION OVER DIFFERENT SPANS OF TIME	SENSORY PERCEPTION OF STREET VENDING ACTIVITIES WITHIN PUBLIC SPACES
Height of Compound Walls	A) FOREGROUND FEATURES :	Footprint, height, shape and size	1. Necessary (items of daily necessity)	Period / Segment of day for operations :	Distinctive calls to advertise wares
Width of Footpath / Sidewalk	Carts/Kiosks form and design	Area required for vendors to operate :	Lead to daily encounters and develops sociability	Morning, Afternoon, Evening, Night	Distinctive smells of wares especially food
Height of Railings / Barricades	Product displays, arrangement of wares / goods	Access to wares / goods, equipment (sitting / standing)	2. Optional (items bought periodically)	Operational hours during that period :	Sense of touch due to compact arrangements in restricted spaces
Width of Parking lane, Carriage Way, Divider	Signage used to add visibility to cart / stall	Area required for customers to circulate :	Lead to chance encounters and develops familiarity	Number of Hours per Day	Distinctive tastes of food items
Height and Spread of Street lights	B) BACKGROUND FEATURES :	Access to stall, products, vendor (standing / moving)	3. Social (shopping as a social activity)	Variation in Volume of Vending Activity (customers / hour)	IMAGIBILITY OF PUBLIC SPACES THAT HOST STREET VENDING
Distance between Trees and size of canopy	Condition of Compound Walls	Area required for storage, equipment, etc.	Lead to intended opportunities for socializing	Maximum Footfall hours	Perception of street vending contributing to the public space:
Availability of other Street Furniture	Character of Building Facades	Area required for waste disposal, etc.	4. Public Perception of vending activities	Average Footfall hours	Towards more sociability and interactions
Availability of Public Toilets and Waste Collection	Interaction with formal Shops : 1. Inclusion 2. Exclusion	Distance / Extent of circulation (territory) for Mobile Vendors	a. Congestion of surroundings OR b. Convenience of service	Historical presence of Vending Activities at the location	Towards value addition to urban life by providing convenience and diversity of access to goods and services
Availability of physical Infrastructure			5. Value addition to urban life		Towards more congestion and chaos

 PHYSICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF VENDING LOCATIONS The characteristics of the public spaces / streets such as compound walls, footpaths, railings, etc.	 FOREGROUND - BACKGROUND The components that make the foreground of the stall juxtaposed against the components of public space that provide the background	 AREA REQUIRED Length, Width and Height dimensions required for stall to function	 CONGESTION OR CONVENIENCE The time span during which vending activities are operational	 TIME & DURATION The time span during which vending activities are operational	 REGULATIONS The regulatory frameworks that shape the public space
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Figure 7: Six dimensions of urban design (Source: Author)

Physical Characteristics of Vending Locations:

The characteristics of public spaces / streets such as compound walls, footpaths, railings, etc.

Foreground - Background:

The components that make the foreground of the stall juxtaposed against the components of public space that provide the background

Area Required:

Length, Width and Height dimensions required for stall to function

Congestion or Convenience:

The time span during which vending activities are operational

Time and Duration:

The time span during which vending activities are operational

Regulations:

The regulatory frameworks that shape the public spaces

3.3 Length of Frontage of Plots:

Situation A:

Long frontage plots, larger distances between entry / exit points. This presents fewer opportunities for people to pause to interact while walking along the street, resulting in fewer opportunities for vendors to attract customers.

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Figure 8: Large frontage plots and larger distances between entry/exit points (Source: Author)

Situation B:

Short frontage plots, short distance between entry / exit points. This presents more opportunities for people to pause to interact while walking along the street, resulting in more opportunities for vendors to attract customers.

Figure 9: Short frontage plots and shorter distance between entry/exit points (Source: Author)

In *Life between Buildings*, Jan Ghel highlights the inverse relationship between length of frontage of plots and number of opportunities for social interaction observed along that frontage.

3.4 Surveys of Customers:

Figure 10: Frequency of buying from street vendors (Source: Author)

While high footfall is a prerequisite condition for vending activities to be observed in any urban locality, the survey brings to light that higher levels of vending are observed in residential localities.

Figure 11: Vicinity to street vendors from residence or workplace (Source: Author)

It also suggests that the majority of such vending activity centred on items of daily necessity such as groceries.

Figure 12: Number of street vendors near residence or workplace (Source: Author)

It further informs that the social interactions of customers with vendors are predominantly focused on the prices of products and fluctuations in these.

Sections of Vending Streets:

Figure 13: Sections of vending streets (Source: Author)

In Seeking Spatial Justice, Edward W. Soja argues that in urban areas all inhabitants of the city should have the right to not only access public space, but should also to shape this space equitably.

Distribution of Street Vending Activities:

	TYPOLOGY OF VENDING ZONES	DENSITY	DIVERSITY		M	P	F	DURATION
SPARSE	PUBLIC SPACES SILVER BEACH JUHU CHOWPATY JUHU BEACH CARTER ROAD	AVERAGE DENSITY OF VENDORS FOR A STRETCH OF 500mIS OBSERVED TO BE BETWEEN 5 TO 10 (<10)	QUICK SNACKS	✓				06:00 HRS TO 10:00 HRS 16:00 HRS TO 22:00 HRS 22:00 HRS TO 02:00 HRS
			PACKAGED DRINKING WATER	✓				
			SMALL TOYS	✓				
			INSTANT PHOTOGRAPH SELLERS	✓				
			TEA/COFFEE (MOBILE)	✓				
	NATURAL MARKETS JP ROAD, ANDHERI WEST R G GADKARI MARG, IRLA JUHU ROAD, SANTACRUZ WEST LINKING ROAD, BANDRA WEST	AVERAGE DENSITY OF VENDORS FOR A STRETCH OF 500mIS OBSERVED TO BE BETWEEN 10 TO 20 (<20)	QUICK SNACKS	✓		✓		08:00 HRS TO 10:00 HRS 12:00 HRS TO 15:00 HRS 16:00 HRS TO 19:00 HRS
			FAST FOOD	✓		✓	✓	
			PACKAGED DRINKING WATER	✓			✓	
			TEA/COFFEE	✓			✓	
			ELECTRONICS AND MOBILE ACCESSORIES	✓		✓		
			STATIONERY	✓		✓		
			COBBLERS	✓			✓	
	STREETS VEERA DESAI ROAD, ANDHERI WEST SAMARTH RAMDAS MARG, JVPD TAGORE ROAD, SANTACRUZ WEST HILL ROAD, BANDRA WEST	AVERAGE DENSITY OF VENDORS FOR A STRETCH OF 500mIS OBSERVED TO BE BETWEEN 20 TO 30 (<30)	QUICK SNACKS	✓		✓		09:00 HRS TO 21:00 HRS 16:00 HRS TO 20:00 HRS
			FAST FOOD	✓			✓	
			PACKAGED DRINKING WATER	✓			✓	
TEA/COFFEE			✓		✓	✓		
ELECTRONICS AND MOBILE ACCESSORIES			✓		✓			
TOYS (SMALL AND LARGE)			✓		✓			
STATIONERY			✓		✓			
GARMENTS, SHOES, BAGS AND BELTS			✓			✓		
RAILWAY STATIONS ANDHERI STATION WEST VILE PARLE STATION WEST SANTACRUZ STATION WEST BANDRA STATION WEST	AVERAGE DENSITY OF VENDORS FOR A STRETCH OF 500mIS OBSERVED TO BE BETWEEN 30 TO 50 (<50)	QUICK SNACKS	✓		✓		08:00 HRS TO 12:00 HRS 10:00 HRS TO 22:00 HRS 16:00 HRS TO 20:00 HRS	
		FAST FOOD	✓			✓		
		PACKAGED DRINKING WATER	✓			✓		
		TEA/COFFEE	✓		✓	✓		
		GREEN GROCERIES	✓		✓			
		ELECTRONICS AND MOBILE ACCESSORIES	✓		✓			
		TOYS (SMALL AND LARGE)	✓		✓			
		STATIONERY	✓			✓		
		GARMENTS, SHOES, BAGS AND BELTS	✓			✓		
		BARBERS	✓			✓		
		COBBLERS	✓		✓			
		TAILORS	✓		✓			
DENSE	AVERAGE DENSITY OF VENDORS FOR A STRETCH OF 500mIS OBSERVED TO BE BETWEEN 50 TO 100 (>50)	APPLIANCE REPAIRMEN	✓			✓		
		KITCHEN UTENSILS AND CUTLERY	✓			✓		

Figure 14: Distribution of street vending activities (Source: Author)

3.5 Inferences:

Convergent and Divergent Zones of Street Vending Identified:

The research studies parameters such as the volume, direction of movement and diversity of footfall, presence of land use magnets that attract footfall, and length of frontage of plots along streets through indicators such as the density, diversity and duration of street vending activities, and identifies two distinct categories of public spaces based on the type and mode of street vending conducted within them:

Convergent Zones: Where the predominant land uses bring footfall to these areas, converging it into the available public spaces

Figure 15: Convergent zones (Source: Author)

In such zones the dominant patterns of street vending are Circuits, where individual vendors have defined zones or territories of movement

Divergent Zones: Where the predominant land uses bring footfall *through* these areas, *diverging* it across the available public spaces

Figure 16: Divergent zones (Source: Author)

In such zones the dominant patterns of street vending are Networks, where street vending activities appear in continuing clusters spanning over a larger area. The research uses the predominant land uses and the direction and movement of footfall to or through a locality, to identify the direct relationship between the typologies of street vending activities and the type of land use that is predominant in that locality as illustrated by these two distinctly observable patterns.

Thus, *Circuits of Street Vending* that are usually observed in localities and neighbourhoods that are categorized as *Convergent Zones*, whereas *Networks of Street Vending* that are usually observed in localities and neighbourhoods that are categorized as *Divergent Zones*.

4. Conclusions:

Street vendors show a great degree of innovation, adaptability and resilience to legislative hurdles and political fluctuations that they encounter frequently, as well as to the spatial constraints of the physical environment that they inhabit to conduct their livelihoods. This is evident in the myriad variations of displaying their wares suited to the available space and its characteristics. This research further demonstrates that beyond the morphology of a space, vending activity also significantly depends on numerous other factors that determine the category and distribution of street vending in that space.

While footfall remains the foremost among these, factors such as dominant land use and length of plot frontage also have substantial influence on the patterns of street vending activity supported within a space. The research thus identifies *Convergent and Divergent Zones* for vending and determines the predominant form of vending within each zone as being in *Circuits or Networks* respectively. The research suggests that in order to better address street vending in public spaces, the above framework can be applied to individually to different areas and based on the category and distribution of vending identified, a customized set of regulatory guidelines should be adopted for each area rather than applying a standard set of regulations across the entire city.

5. Recommendations:

The conclusions of the research provide a substantial degree of clarity on the approach that needs to be adopted to create regulatory frameworks and controls that suitably address the needs and concerns of urban street vending activities. Further, the research recommends that in order to ensure the smooth operation and integration of street vending activities into the public spaces within which they are conducted, while also ensuring that these do not impact the other public activities that are supported by these shared spaces, it is necessary to study the areas where vending is conducted and determine their typology as *convergent zones* or *divergent zones*, and identify the *circuits of vending* or the *networks of vending* respectively, that are formed as the street vending activities are conducted.

The regulatory framework and controls that suitably address the variety of activities contained within any particular public space, including street vending, need to be responsive to the pattern of street vending supported by that public space. This necessitates the application of a customized set of controls that are specific to not only the street vending activities being conducted in a particular public space, but also their patterns, and the spatial characteristics of that particular public space.

The research therefore proposes a *Regulatory Tool Kit* that has specific regulations that address these diverse characteristics of the public space and the street vending activities hosted within them. The intent of this regulatory tool kit is to make available a wide variety of control options that can be selected and customized to address the specific needs of a particular public space, locality, neighbourhood or geographical area based on its spatial needs.

Conflict of Interest:

The authors have no conflict of interest to declare.

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- Sara Recchi, Department of Sociology and Social Research, University of Milan–Bicocca,
- Sara Recchi, Department of Sociology and Social Research, University of Milan–Bicocca,
- Sara Recchi, Department of Sociology and Social Research, University of Milan–Bicocca,
- Sara Recchi, Department of Sociology and Social Research, University of Milan–Bicocca, Milan, Italy
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